

Van der Waals interactions in solids using the exchange-hole dipole moment model

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(Dated: 9 April 2012)

The exchange-hole dipole moment (XDM) model of dispersion interactions of Becke and Johnson [J. Chem. Phys. **127** (2007) 154108] is implemented for calculations in solids using the pseudopotentials/plane-waves approach. The resulting functional retains the simplicity and efficiency of semilocal functionals while accurately treating dispersion interactions via a semiempirical asymptotic expansion. The dispersion coefficients are calculated completely *ab initio* using local quantities alone (density, gradient, laplacian, and kinetic energy density). The two empirical parameters in the damping function are calculated by fit to a 65-molecule training set recalculated under periodic boundary conditions. Calculations in simple solids offer good results with minimal computational cost compared to the electronic relaxation.

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I. INTRODUCTION

The failure of semilocal functionals to describe dispersion interactions was demonstrated almost 20 years ago¹. Given the broad success and computational feasibility of semilocal DFT, this shortcoming has since been a subject of ever-increasing interest. In a typical wave-function-based calculation, dispersion can be captured, in principle, by increasing the level of theory applied. Indeed, the traditional London picture of dispersion—that of interacting instantaneous dipoles in otherwise zero-dipole molecular fragments—is translated into configuration space language as dipole-dipole interactions of excited molecular states. However, the wave-function approach is computationally demanding: simple methods like MP2 yield poor results (systematic overbinding²) while CCSD(T) (the gold standard for dispersion) presents an unacceptable N^7 scaling with system size. The scaling problem is exacerbated in solids because of their condensed nature³. Although approximate wave-function calculations in solids are possible, for instance, using the incremental method^{4–6} or local-MP2⁷, in the usual plane-wave/pseudopotentials scheme even calculating the HF-like exact exchange is expensive, and correlated wave-function methods are unaffordable.

Several methods have been proposed to include dispersion interactions (see, for instance, refs. 2,8,9 for a review). A non-exhaustive list includes: the random phase approximation (RPA)^{10,11} and non-local correlation functionals based on the adiabatic connection fluctuation-dissipation theorem (ACFDT), like the vdW-DF method^{12–14}, dispersion-corrected potentials (DCPs)^{15–18} and exchange-correlation functionals adapted to treat dispersion by parameter fitting^{19,20}. Each of these methods has its drawbacks either in terms of flexibility, complexity, accuracy, or computational cost.

Because systems where dispersion interactions are important tend to be large, the most popular approach today is an *a posteriori* correction to the DFT energy:

$$E = E_{\text{DFT}} + E_{\text{disp}} \tag{1}$$
$$E_{\text{disp}} = -\frac{1}{2} \sum_{ij} \frac{C_6 f_6(R_{ij})}{R_{ij}^6} + \dots \tag{2}$$

where the dispersion term assumes the London expression and f_6 is the *damping function* (see below).

The fundamental quantities in equation 2 are the dispersion coefficients, C_n . They can be obtained from experimental dipole oscillator strength measurements for molecules, or

calculated using a variety of approaches. In the simplest method, atomic C_6 are extracted from experimental or high-quality calculated molecular values: this is the basis of the DFT-D method²¹⁻²⁴. A drawback is that in a real system, C_6 depend on the molecular environment and, in particular, on the partial charge (directly related to the polarizability) of an atom²⁵. Therefore, it is particularly important to take this effect into account in solids, where ionized interacting fragments are common. Several methods that deal with this problem include the new DFT-D (DFT-D3), and those of Tkatchenko and Scheffler²⁶ and Sato and Nakai²⁷.

In this article, we present the first application to solids of the exchange-hole dipole moment (XDM) model of dispersion interactions of Becke and Johnson²⁸⁻³⁵, that allows fully *ab initio* calculation of dispersion coefficients. It has been shown recently^{8,36,37} that this model combined with a pure density functional yields good results for the calculation of molecular interactions, and we show herein that it holds great promise for condensed phases as well.

II. THE XDM MODEL AND ITS IMPLEMENTATION IN SOLID-STATE

In the XDM model²⁸⁻³⁵, the dispersion interaction energy between molecular fragments is calculated as the electrostatic interaction between dipoles formed by electrons and their associated exchange-holes. In a single-determinant wave-function, the exchange hole:

$$h_{X\sigma}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}') = -\frac{|\rho_{1\sigma}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}')|^2}{\rho_{\sigma}(\mathbf{r})} \quad (3)$$

represents the depletion of probability of finding same-spin electrons assuming a reference electron is at \mathbf{r} , because of Pauli's exclusion principle ($\rho_{1\sigma}$ and ρ_{σ} are the σ -spin first-order density matrix and electron density respectively). The basic quantity in the XDM model is (the square of) the magnitude of the dipole moment of the electron plus its hole ($d_{X\sigma}^2$), where:

$$\mathbf{d}_{X\sigma}(\mathbf{r}) = \int \mathbf{r}' h_{X\sigma}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}') d\mathbf{r}' - \mathbf{r} \quad (4)$$

Assuming that $\mathbf{d}_{X\sigma}(\mathbf{r})$ is oriented towards the closest associated nucleus, it is possible to compute atomic expectation values of the squared multipoles using:

$$\langle M_l^2 \rangle_i = \sum_{\sigma} \int \omega_i(\mathbf{r}) \rho_{\sigma}(\mathbf{r}) [r_i^l - (r_i - d_{X\sigma})^l]^2 d\mathbf{r} \quad (5)$$

where ρ_{σ} is the σ -spin electron density, i labels an atom, r_i is the distance to the atom and ω_i is any appropriate weight function that provides the atomic partition. In this work, we

use the Hirshfeld³⁸ partition method:

$$\omega_i(\mathbf{r}) = \frac{\rho_i^{\text{at}}(\mathbf{r})}{\sum_j \rho_j^{\text{at}}(\mathbf{r})} \quad (6)$$

with ρ_i^{at} the ground state electron density of atom i in its neutral configuration. Using second-order perturbation theory it has been shown that the dispersion coefficients can be calculated using:

$$C_{6,ij} = \frac{\alpha_i \alpha_j \langle M_1^2 \rangle_i \langle M_1^2 \rangle_j}{\langle M_1^2 \rangle_i \alpha_j + \langle M_1^2 \rangle_j \alpha_i} \quad (7)$$

$$C_{8,ij} = \frac{3 \alpha_i \alpha_j (\langle M_1^2 \rangle_i \langle M_2^2 \rangle_j + \langle M_2^2 \rangle_i \langle M_1^2 \rangle_j)}{2 (\langle M_1^2 \rangle_i \alpha_j + \langle M_1^2 \rangle_j \alpha_i)} \quad (8)$$

$$C_{10,ij} = 2 \frac{\alpha_i \alpha_j (\langle M_1^2 \rangle_i \langle M_3^2 \rangle_j + \langle M_3^2 \rangle_i \langle M_1^2 \rangle_j)}{\langle M_1^2 \rangle_i \alpha_j + \langle M_1^2 \rangle_j \alpha_i} + \frac{21}{5} \frac{\alpha_i \alpha_j \langle M_2^2 \rangle_i \langle M_2^2 \rangle_j}{\langle M_1^2 \rangle_i \alpha_j + \langle M_1^2 \rangle_j \alpha_i} \quad (9)$$

The α_i quantity is the atomic polarizability of atom i in the molecule, which is determined by using the linear relationship of polarizability with volume³⁹:

$$\alpha_i = \frac{\int r^3 \omega_i(\mathbf{r}) \rho(\mathbf{r}) d\mathbf{r}}{\int r^3 \rho_{i,\text{free}}(\mathbf{r}) d\mathbf{r}} \alpha_{i,\text{free}} \quad (10)$$

The subscript *free* denotes in vacuo atomic densities and polarizabilities.

The exact expression for the exchange hole involves a double summation over occupied orbitals and is too unwieldy to be used in solids. To avoid this expression, we make use of the exchange-hole model proposed by Becke and Roussel⁴⁰ (BR). In the BR model, the exchange-hole is represented by a simple exponential, $-Ae^{-ar}$, centered at a distance b from the reference point. The parameters A , a and b are obtained by imposing three conditions: normalization ($\int h_{X\sigma}(\mathbf{r}_1, \mathbf{r}_2) d\mathbf{r}_2 = -1$ for all \mathbf{r}_1), and the model having the exact value and curvature of the hole at the reference point. Under these constraints, the b parameter is:

$$b^3 = \frac{x^3 e^{-x}}{8\pi\rho_\sigma} \quad (11)$$

with x determined as the solution of the non-linear equation:

$$\frac{x e^{-2x/3}}{x-2} = \frac{2}{3} \pi^{2/3} \frac{\rho_\sigma^{5/3}}{Q_\sigma} \quad (12)$$

The curvature Q_σ is given in terms of the kinetic energy density (τ_σ):

$$Q_\sigma = \frac{1}{6} (\nabla^2 \rho_\sigma - 2D_\sigma) \quad (13)$$

$$D_\sigma = \tau_\sigma - \frac{1}{4} \frac{(\nabla \rho_\sigma)^2}{\rho_\sigma} \quad (14)$$

$$\tau_\sigma = \sum_i (\nabla \psi_{i\sigma})^2 \quad (15)$$

Using the BR hole, the dipole moment is $d_{X\sigma} = b$. The BR hole in XDM has been shown to give better results when coupled with pure density functionals than the exact hole⁸. Further advantages are that only local quantities ($\rho, \nabla\rho, \nabla^2\rho$ and τ) are used, effectively turning the dispersion-corrected DFT functional into a meta-GGA, and that the performance of the pure functional in short range interactions is retained.

In the XDM model, the dispersion coefficients are calculated strictly from first principles quantities. To avoid unphysically applying the asymptotic expansion at short range, a damping function is required. Grimme has shown that the form of the damping function is not as important as it being correctly parametrized⁴¹. In this work, we use the damping expression of Becke and Johnson. With this choice, the dispersion energy per cell is:

$$E_{\text{disp}} = -\frac{1}{2} \sum_{\mathbf{L}} \sum'_{ij} \frac{C_{6,ij}}{R_{\text{vdw},ij}^6 + R_{ij\mathbf{L}}^6} + \frac{C_{8,ij}}{R_{\text{vdw},ij}^8 + R_{ij\mathbf{L}}^8} + \frac{C_{10,ij}}{R_{\text{vdw},ij}^{10} + R_{ij\mathbf{L}}^{10}} \quad (16)$$

where the prime excludes the $i = j$ term for lattice vector $\mathbf{L} = \mathbf{0}$. The quantity $R_{\text{vdw},ij}$ measures the range of interaction of the atomic pair ij , in a manner analogous to the sum of the sum of van der Waals radii (hence the labeling). It is calculated as:

$$R_{\text{vdw},ij} = a_1 R_{c,ij} + a_2 \quad (17)$$

with $R_{c,ij}$ being the average critical radius where the C_6 , C_8 and C_{10} contributions are roughly the same magnitude:

$$R_{c,ij} = \frac{1}{3} \left[\left(\frac{C_{8,ij}}{C_{6,ij}} \right)^{1/2} + \left(\frac{C_{10,ij}}{C_{6,ij}} \right)^{1/4} + \left(\frac{C_{10,ij}}{C_{8,ij}} \right)^{1/2} \right] \quad (18)$$

This damping expression contains two adjustable parameters (a_1 and a_2). As we shall see below, it is convenient to reduce it to a one-dimensional damping function by setting $a_1 = 0$ when using particular exchange-correlation functionals.

The performance of the XDM dispersion model using pure functionals has been reviewed recently for molecular calculations^{8,36}. In this work, we present a practical implementation of the model in the context of plane-waves/pseudopotentials calculations of periodic solids. We comment now on the points in which the application to solids differs from molecules.

In order to evaluate the integrals in equations 5 and 10, molecular integration grids are replaced by uniform three-dimensional grids that span the unit cell of the crystal. At each point of the grid, the kinetic energy density, the electron density and its derivatives are

calculated using a three-dimensional Fourier transform and the b parameter is evaluated by applying equations 11, 12 and 13. Likewise, the atomic densities and core densities are evaluated on the same grid. The computation of the atomic moments (equation 5) for each non-equivalent atom in the cell proceeds by summing shells of cells at increasing distance from the origin. The summation stops whenever the central atom contributes less than a certain density cutoff (10^{-12} a. u.) to all grid points in the shell. Then, the dispersion coefficients (eq. 7) are calculated and the dispersion energy (eq. 16) is evaluated. The dispersion contributions to the atomic forces and stresses are calculated under the reasonable assumption⁴² that the dispersion coefficients are approximately constant:

$$\mathbf{F}_{\text{disp},i} = \sum_{\mathbf{L}} \sum_j' \sum_{n=6,8,10} \frac{n C_{n,ij} R_{ij\mathbf{L}}^{n-2}}{(R_{\text{vdw},ij}^n + R_{ij\mathbf{L}}^n)^2} \mathbf{R}_{ij\mathbf{L}} \quad (19)$$

$$\sigma_{\text{disp},\xi\eta} = -\frac{1}{2V} \sum_{\mathbf{L}} \sum_{ij}' \sum_{n=6,8,10} \frac{n C_{n,ij} R_{ij\mathbf{L}}^{n-2} (R_{ij\mathbf{L}})_\xi (R_{ij\mathbf{L}})_\eta}{(R_{\text{vdw},ij}^n + R_{ij\mathbf{L}}^n)^2} \quad (20)$$

where $\mathbf{F}_{\text{disp},i}$ is the dispersion force on atom i , $\sigma_{\text{disp},\xi\eta}$ are two cartesian components of the stress tensor and V is the cell volume.

The computational cost of calculating the dispersion energy is small compared to the electronic SCF. The leading contribution to this cost is the computation of the promolecular densities on the uniform grid. Because of this, the energy, force and stress sums are done over shells around the origin, instead of using a more sophisticated Ewald-like approach.

An important point is that the quantities defining the BR hole (eqs. 11, 12 and 13) are calculated using valence densities and kinetic energy densities. The reconstruction of the all electron density and kinetic energy density is possible in the Projector Augmented Wave (PAW) method⁴³ under the frozen core approximation, but we have opted for simplicity in this first implementation. Intuitively, one would expect that the strongly-bound core electrons have little impact on the exchange-hole dipole moments. The soundness of this assertion is verified *a posteriori*. In contrast, the densities entering the Hirshfeld expressions of weight and atomic volumes are all-electron. Again, we opt for simplicity by approximating the all-electron self-consistent density by simply adding a core contribution that accounts for the missing electrons. In the case that spuriously high values of b are obtained close to the nucleus, the unphysical contribution is prevented by making $r_i - b = 0$ whenever $b > r_i$ in equation 5, enforcing the correct behavior of the hole in this region. This numerical precaution was already used in ref. 34.

As in preceding works^{8,36}, the dispersion correction is used in a post-SCF way. Recent works^{13,42} have shown that there is little difference between this approach and including the dispersion term in the one-electron potential.

III. CALCULATION DETAILS

The XDM model has been implemented in an early stage in the second development of the critic program⁴⁴, and then in a local copy of Quantum ESPRESSO⁴⁵, that has also been modified to include the B86b and PW86 exchange functionals used below.

The coefficients that damp the asymptotic dispersion term (a_1 and a_2 in equation 17) must be parametrized for each exchange-correlation functional. To do so, a training set of reference data with accurate geometries and/or binding energies of non-covalently bound systems is required. Ideally, we would like to use cohesive energies of *real* molecular solids. However, the cohesive energies of these are unknown because of the difficulty of reliably applying the highly accurate wave-function methods, common in the calculation of benchmark-level molecular binding energies, to solids. In addition, the use of experimental sublimation enthalpies presents the problem of reducing the data to static conditions by eliminating the thermal and zero-point contributions.

As a consequence, we turn to use the set of 65 dimers described in Kannemann and Becke⁸, recalculated under periodic boundary conditions and using large supercells to avoid molecular self-interactions. This training set is based on several preceding databases in the literature^{19,32,46-48}. A complete list of dimers, together with supercell sizes, are given in table I of the supplementary information⁴⁹. The cell size has been converged to an accuracy of ≈ 0.01 kcal/mol in the total energy of monomers and dimers separately.

We use the PAW method of Blöchl et al.⁴³, that is formally all-electron but operates under the frozen-core approximation. The atomic PAW datasets are adapted from the atompaw library⁵⁰. To ensure transferability, we have shrunk the radii so that convergence in the total energy is in the order of 0.1 mRy per atom at a plane-wave cutoff of 80 Ry. This energy cutoff is used in all the calculations reported in this article. The core radii for the elements we use are: 0.9 (H), 1.0 (He), 1.1 (C), 1.3 (N), 1.41 (O), 1.51 (F), 1.7 (Ne), 1.6 (Si), 1.51 (S), 1.51 (Cl), 2.1 (Ar), 2.3 (Kr) and 3.5 (Xe). The kinetic energy cutoff for the density expansion used throughout the article is 800 Ry and, contrary to other meta-GGAs,

there is no change in the dispersion energies by refining the density grid. For the molecular systems, only one \mathbf{k} -point at Γ is used. In the case of crystals, the \mathbf{k} -point grids used will be indicated in the next section.

The choice of exchange-correlation functional is also important. A drawback of abandoning the post-HF version of XDM is that the performance of the dispersion correction no longer depends exclusively on the correlation part but also on the quality of the exchange functional³⁶. The dispersion term added to the DFT energy is always attractive and tends to a finite value in the atomic coalescence limit thanks to the damping function. However, this limit is characterized by a steep repulsive wall, that must be provided by the electronic DFT calculation. In the case of closed-shell fragments bound by non-covalent interactions, this repulsive wall originates primarily from the Pauli repulsion of same-spin electrons in different fragments. Common semilocal exchange functionals present different repulsive walls that yield different behaviors in the absence of a dispersion correction: from overly repulsive to spuriously binding³⁶.

If possible, one would want a repulsive wall that mimics HF repulsion because the Pauli repulsion between closed-shell fragments is completely described at the HF level. Because we are interested only in pure functionals, we have explored different options, choosing those functionals that best reproduce HF results in a purely dispersion-bound dimer, such as Ne_2 . This study is analogous to that in ref. 36, except translated into a periodic plane-wave/pseudopotentials calculation. The whole collection of functionals in the LIBXC library by Marques et al.⁵⁹ has been used in a post-SCF way to compute the binding energy curve of the neon dimer. The repulsive walls closest to the HF result are shown in figure 1. It is heartening to verify the close similarity between our result and the equivalent in molecules obtained by Kannemann and Becke³⁶. The functionals yielding repulsive curves closest to HF are B86b and PW86, as already noted by Lacks and Gordon⁶⁰, thanks to the correct trend of the exchange enhancement factors in the high reduced-density gradient limit.

From this figure, we have chosen to proceed using the B86b⁵⁶, PW86⁵⁷, PBE⁵³, revPBE⁵⁴ and PBEsol⁵⁵ exchange functionals, all paired with PBE dynamical correlation⁵³. The PBE correlation functional is a popular choice in solid-state because of its good performance. The first two exchange functionals give the results closest to the HF energy curve. The others are very common in solid-state calculations and are ever-present in almost all electronic structure codes under periodic boundary conditions. An important warning is that the

FIG. 1. Potential energy curves for the neon dimer with selected exchange-only methods. The HF energy was calculated self-consistently using the basis-set free NUMOL program^{51,52}. The exchange functionals represented are LDA, Perdew-Burke-Ernzerhof (PBE)⁵³, revised PBE (revPBE)⁵⁴, PBEsol⁵⁵, Becke(86) (B86b)⁵⁶ Perdew-Wang(86) (PW86)⁵⁷ and the reparametrization of B97⁵⁸ for use with the dispersion correction of Grimme (B97D)²².

PW86 functional presents numerical noise in the expansion region of the energy curve. This noise, also present in molecular calculations, precludes the usage of the functional in self-consistent supercell calculations. The PW86 results presented in the following section are obtained using the PBE density and calculating the exchange-correlation energy in a post-SCF manner.

IV. PARAMETRIZATION OF THE DAMPING FUNCTION

A damping function is necessary to deactivate the asymptotic expression of the dispersion interaction (eq. 2) at short range. The use of a damping function introduces a number of empirical parameters that need to be determined using a training set. For each of the exchange-correlation functionals chosen, we calculate the interaction coefficients (C_n) and

FIG. 2. MAPE for the B86b functional as a function of the damping parameters. The (unique) minimum is marked by a cross, and corresponds to $a_1 = 0.136$ and $a_2 = 3.178 \text{ \AA}$, with a MAPE of 15.5.

the critical radii (R_c) at the reference molecular geometries. These are non-empirical and therefore need to be calculated only once. The binding energies for the dimers are then functions of the adjustable parameters a_1 and a_2 .

Figure 2 shows the evolution of the mean absolute percentage error (MAPE) with a_1 and a_2 for the B86b functional. The figures for the other functionals are equivalent in shape. There is a linear relationship between the a_1 and a_2 parameters, that supports the soundness of using the van der Waals radii in equation 16. Within the valley of good a_1 and a_2 values, the MAPE variation is much slower than in the complementary direction. A unique minimum, corresponding to the optimum parameters, is found in this valley. Its position depends on the functional used, in agreement with their varying repulsive behavior.

The optimum parameters for the five functionals considered are presented in table I. The PW86 coefficients are close to those reported in ref. 8 ($a_1 = 0.82$ and $a_2 = 1.16 \text{ \AA}$). The calculated MAPE (16.9) is a little worse than the equivalent in the molecular study (12.6) but still better than the version using the exact exchange hole (19.9). This slight degradation of the performance may be attributed tentatively to the neglect of the core contribution

TABLE I. Optimized damping parameters for the five exchange-correlation functionals, number of dimers used in the training set (N) and some statistical measures of the goodness of the fit (defined in the text).

	B86b	PW86	PBE	revPBE	PBEsol
a_1	0.136	0.881	0.000	0.316	0.000
$a_2(\text{\AA})$	3.178	0.937	3.879	2.065	4.185
N	65	65	49	49	49
MAE (kcal/mol)	0.41	0.47	0.61	0.65	0.88
MAPE	15.5	16.9	16.9	16.6	20.8

in the calculation of the atomic moments. B86b performs a little better than PW86 and achieves the minimum MAPE (15.5%) of all the considered functionals. The dispersion-energy correction and its derivatives can be implemented together with the ionic relaxation, enabling us to perform geometry optimizations of the crystal. In addition, the performance of B86b for hard (covalently bound) materials is similar to other GGAs, as expected from its reduced-density gradient enhancement factor, which is intermediate between PBE and PBEsol⁶¹.

In the case of PBE, PBEsol and revPBE, the binding energies of the noble gas dimers are dominated by the spurious binding coming from the exchange functional. Because the dispersion correction is always attractive, the inclusion of these dimers in the training set incorporates data points that are always wrong, independent of the values of a_1 and a_2 . The unphysical behavior of these values controls the fit. Consequently, we have decided to remove the dimers containing noble gases from the training set. Even then, accounting for the excessive binding in E_{DFT} yields negative optimum a_1 values. This behavior is unphysical and we have opted for setting $a_1 = 0$ for PBE and PBEsol, effectively reducing the damping to a one-parameter expression (a_2). Even so, the MAPE for PBEsol is worse than those of the other functionals.

A detailed relation of the calculated binding energies using the optimized parameters is presented in table I of the supplementary⁴⁹ information and graphically in figure 3. The worst results are obtained for PBE, revPBE and PBEsol in the dimers involving noble gases because of the spurious binding of these functionals. In contrast, the results for the noble

FIG. 3. Graphical display of the relative error in the calculated binding energies for the 65 dimers. The label B86b(opt) corresponds to the binding energies calculated by optimizing the geometry using the parameters in table I. .

gases in PW86 and B86b are not particularly bad compared to the rest of dimers. Regarding the non-rare-gas dimers, the results are particularly good in the hydrogen-bonded (water dimer to adenine/thymine dimer) and naphthalene dimers.

In order to check how geometric relaxation of the dimers affects the calculated binding energies, we have fully relaxed the dimers (intra- and inter-molecular geometry) using the B86b functional. The results are presented in figure 3. The reoptimized binding energies are close to those calculated at fixed geometries, except in the NH_3/NH_3 and $\text{NH}_3/\text{benzene}$ dimers, where the agreement with the reference values is improved by optimization. The orientation of the monomers in these cases are very similar before and after the relaxation. The MAE (MAPE) of B86b with full relaxation of the geometry is 0.44 kcal/mol (16.0%), only 0.03 kcal/mol (0.5%) higher than the unrelaxed values.

Another interesting point is that the higher order terms in the dispersion expansion (C_8 and C_{10}) improve the agreement with the reference binding energies. For instance, the damping parameters obtained for the B86b functional using only the C_6 term in the asymptotic expansion become unphysical ($a_1 = -0.360$ and $a_2 = 3.716$) and the MAPE increases to 21.86 (c.f. 15.5 in table I). This clearly suggests that the higher-order terms contribute appreciably to the accuracy of the XDM model, which is consistent with other results in the literature²⁷.

The S22 benchmark⁴⁷, containing CCSD(T) level binding energies extrapolated to the

complete basis set limit, is routinely used to assess the accuracy in the representation of non-covalent interactions. The MAE in our implementation of XDM (kcal/mol) are: 0.62 (B86b), 0.74 (PW86), 0.75 (PBE), 0.57 (revPBE), and 1.05 (PBEsol). These values are in the range of those reported for DFT-D2²³ and other methods (see table 4 in ref. 8), although higher than the corresponding values for XDM in molecules (0.36 kcal/mol). It must be noted that the data in the literature generally comes from parameter fits to the S22 set itself while we have used a training set two to three times larger. As a consequence, our MAE and MAPE for S22 increases, but our parameters provide greater generality in the calculation of real systems. Improved statistics can be obtained by refitting the damping parameters to the S22 set alone. In this case, the MAE drops except for revPBE: 0.42 (B86b), 0.43 (PW86), 0.55 (PBE), 0.59 (revPBE), and 0.98 (PBEsol).

V. RESULTS FOR SIMPLE SOLIDS

In this section, the newly-implemented XDM model is applied to some simple molecular solids. To measure the accuracy of our model, we compare to the experimental geometries that, except for the rare-gas solids, have *not* been corrected for zero-point or thermal effects. This is clearly a limitation and we are currently in the process of compiling sublimation enthalpy data to perform rigorous benchmarking involving cohesive energies. Benchmarking of a semiempirical approach with fixed C_6 for a few solids was performed by Ortmann et al.⁶² and of the vdw-DF in hard simple solids by Klimes et al.⁶¹.

The systems were chosen to span a range of intermolecular interactions (dispersion, dipole-dipole, hydrogen bonding) and are composed of solids where dispersion interactions are essential to determine the geometry. The chosen solids, together with the \mathbf{k} -point meshes used in the calculation are: carbon dioxide ($4 \times 4 \times 4$), ammonia ($4 \times 4 \times 4$), dinitrogen ($4 \times 4 \times 4$), acetic acid ($2 \times 2 \times 2$), urea ($2 \times 2 \times 2$), graphite ($16 \times 16 \times 8$) and the noble-gas fcc crystals of Ne, Ar, and Kr (all three with $4 \times 4 \times 4$). The chosen \mathbf{k} grids are sufficiently dense to converge the total energy and the XDM dispersion energy.

Table II compares the calculated geometries (using B86b and PW86 functionals) with experimental data. The column marked PBE-D corresponds to the results obtained combining the DFT-D2 approach of Grimme²² with the PBE functional²⁴, the canonical implementation of the semi-empirical dispersion correction in Quantum ESPRESSO. Except

TABLE II. Calculated geometries of molecular crystals with selected XDM methods or PBE-D, compared to experimental results (the reference follows the crystal name). Cell lengths are in angstrom and atomic positions are in crystal coordinates (for clarity, the atomic positions of urea and acetic acid have been left out). All structures except ammonia were obtained from the Crystallography Open Database (COD)⁶³. In the case of the noble-gas crystals, the lattice constants have been corrected for zero-point and thermal effects using a Debye model (see ref. 4). The first three columns presenting calculated data give absolute values (and MAE) and the other three, percentage deviations referred to the experimental reference (and MA%E).

Crystal		Expt.	B86b	PW86	PBE-D	B86b%	PW86%	PBE-D%	
CO ₂ ⁶⁴	[<i>Pa</i> $\bar{3}$]	<i>a</i>	5.624	5.733	5.584	5.649	1.94	-0.71	0.44
	O (x,x,x)	<i>x</i>	0.119	0.118	0.122	0.120	-0.84	2.52	0.84
NH ₃ ⁶⁵	[<i>P2</i> ₁ 3]	<i>a</i>	5.131	5.014	4.997	4.888	-2.28	-2.61	-4.74
	N (x,x,x)	<i>x</i>	0.211	0.207	0.207	0.209	-1.90	-1.90	0.95
	H (x,y,z)	<i>x</i>	0.369	0.374	0.375	0.377	1.36	1.63	2.17
		<i>y</i>	0.267	0.269	0.269	0.278	0.75	0.75	4.12
	<i>z</i>	0.116	0.107	0.107	0.103	-7.76	-7.76	-11.21	
N ₂ ⁶⁶	[<i>Pa</i> $\bar{3}$]	<i>a</i>	5.644	5.657	5.532	5.597	0.23	-1.98	-0.83
	N (x,x,x)	<i>x</i>	0.054	0.056	0.058	0.057	3.70	7.41	5.56
Acetic acid ⁶⁷	[<i>Pna</i> 2 ₁]	<i>a</i>	13.151	13.297	13.296	13.149	1.11	1.10	-0.02
		<i>b</i>	3.923	3.698	3.626	3.468	-5.74	-7.57	-11.60
		<i>c</i>	5.762	5.994	5.998	6.053	4.02	4.09	5.05
Urea ⁶⁸	[<i>P</i> $\bar{4}$ 2 ₁ <i>m</i>]	<i>a</i>	5.661	5.588	5.574	5.447	-1.29	-1.54	-3.78
		<i>c</i>	4.712	4.661	4.671	4.662	-1.08	-0.87	-1.06
Graphite ⁶⁹	[<i>P6</i> ₃ <i>mc</i>]	<i>a</i>	2.456	2.461	2.467	2.466	0.20	0.45	0.41
		<i>c</i>	6.696	6.634	6.851	6.429	-0.93	2.31	-3.99
Ne ⁴	[fcc]	<i>a</i>	4.35	4.626	4.229	4.252	6.34	-2.78	-2.25
Ar ⁴	[fcc]	<i>a</i>	5.23	5.490	5.405	5.352	4.97	3.35	2.33
Kr ⁴	[fcc]	<i>a</i>	5.61	5.609	5.609	5.674	-0.02	-0.02	1.14
Cell length MA(%E)				0.121	0.120	0.145	2.32	2.26	2.90
Int. coord. MA(%E)				0.004	0.005	0.007	2.72	3.66	4.14

for CO₂, Ne, and Ar, the XDM model with the B86b functional improves upon PBE-D in the calculation of the cell lengths involving intermolecular interactions (e.g. c in graphite). Consistent with the binding energies obtained for the dimers, the geometries of the rare-gas solids (Ar and particularly Ne) are slightly off the experimental value: the average absolute cell length deviations are 3.8% (B86b), 2.0% (PW86) and 1.9% (PBE-D), with a maximum deviation of 6.3% for the B86b cell length of Ar. It is important to note that three-body and higher-order contributions are important in the description of noble-gas crystals⁷⁰, and are not included in the XDM model, which is restricted to second-order perturbation theory (incorporating these higher-order terms may be more difficult than incorporating further additive terms because of problems at the density functional level, see ref. 71). Note, however, that the coefficients reported by Grimme²² were optimized together with a particular exchange-correlation functional (B97D) that is not available in the current implementation of the program.

For the hard cell directions (i.e. those that involve covalent interactions), the three functionals reduce to common GGA behavior, which is rather accurate. It is satisfying to verify that the dispersion correction barely affects the geometry of cell lengths dominated by covalent interactions and of atomic positions (controlled by intramolecular interactions). This is reasonable because the dispersion interaction is small compared to the energy variation scale of the typical covalent energy minimum⁴². Dispersion forces are only important in cases where the binding energy curve is shallow, again illustrating the importance of avoiding spurious binding in the uncorrected DFT energy¹.

Graphite is a popular dispersion-bound solid. Because of its simplicity, it serves as a benchmark for new computational methods while, at the same time, both graphite and graphene are very important in technological applications. The exfoliation energy of graphite (the energy necessary to infinitely strain hexagonal graphite in the c direction) calculated with XDM is presented in figure 4 and compared to experimental results and other calculations. XDM, with the five functionals studied in this article, provides cell lengths that agree with reference data to within 0.5 Å and an exfoliation energies accurate to within 10 meV. This energy range is comparable to the precision of the latest experimental result⁷³. The predicted geometries and energies are in much better agreement with experiment than previous results using semiempirical corrections to DFT or the vdW-DF functional. The accuracy is comparable to ACFDT-RPA and QMC but, of course, with a much reduced

FIG. 4. The exfoliation energy of graphite calculated with selected XDM methods, compared to experimental results^{72,73}, LDA⁶², GGA with empirical corrections (GGA+vdw)^{24,62,74}, ACFDT in the RPA approach (ACFDT-RPA)⁷⁵, Quantum Monte Carlo (QMC)⁷⁶, and the vdw-DF functional (vdw-DF)⁷⁷⁻⁸⁰. Uncorrected GGAs barely bind graphite such that the results are not in the plot range. The experimental lattice constant⁶⁶ and binding energies have not been corrected for zero-point effects.

computational cost. The C_{33} elastic constant measure the curvature of the energy along the exfoliation path. Their calculated GGA-XDM values (in GPa) are 40.7 (B86b), 32.6 (PW86), 29.5 (PBE), 39.8 (PBEsol) and 52.9 (revPBE). While the spread is higher than for lattice constants and exfoliation energies, the results still compare well to experimental results (36.5–40.7⁸¹⁻⁸⁴) relative to previous theoretical predictions: 13¹⁴, 25⁸⁰, 27⁷⁹ and 36.4⁸⁰ (vdw-DF); 41.7⁶² and 62⁷⁴ (DFT-D); and 36⁷⁵ (RPA).

The results above confirm the XDM model as a comparatively accurate and cost-efficient method in the semilocal DFT plus plane-waves/pseudopotentials framework.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

In this article, we presented the implementation of the exchange-hole dipole moment (XDM) model in condensed matter calculations. Using the XDM model, it is possible to calculate non-empirical dispersion coefficients from local quantities. A damping function is necessary to limit the interaction at shorter distances, which in turn must be parametrized. This was done by performing calculations for a training set of 65 molecular dimers, under periodic boundary conditions. Five different functionals (B86b, PW86, PBE, PBEsol, and revPBE exchange, all paired with PBE correlation) were considered and the corresponding damping coefficients were found by least-squares fitting.

The functionals that give the lowest combined error for the training set (B86b and PW86) are those that best reproduce the HF repulsive wall, and also those that present error minima at physical values of the parametrization coefficients. The total error is slightly worse than in the case of molecular calculations, which can be attributed to the neglect of the core contribution to the electron density and kinetic-energy density in the calculation of the atomic dipole moments.

We tested the new implementation by calculating the geometries of a small set of dispersion-bound crystals. It was found that, using the B86b functional, it is possible to obtain geometries in close agreement with experiment and, in general, improve upon the canonical semiempirical dispersion correction in Quantum ESPRESSO (PBE-D). In addition, the excellent accuracy of GGA functionals for the covalent bond lengths is retained. The XDM approach also gives excellent results in the calculation of the equilibrium geometry and exfoliation energy of graphite, comparable to methods with a much greater computational cost.

VII. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

AOR thanks the Spanish Malta/Consolider initiative (no. CSD2007-00045).

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